

Conference Abstract

Dactylorhiza kalopissii (Liliopsida: Orchidaceae) in Bulgaria: Distribution and conservation status

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Abstract

The Balkan sub-endemic species *Dactylorhiza kalopissii* E. Nelson is distributed in Bulgaria, Greece and North Macedonia. It has a local distribution and inhabits alkaline fens, wet meadows, and mountain rivulet banks. This orchid is a globally endangered species, included in Annex IIb of the Council Directive 92/43 EEC. It was first reported for Bulgaria in 1991 and until 2008 it was known only from this single locality in the country. Here we summarize the recent data on the distribution of the species in Bulgaria, the population numbers and their fluctuation in time. During the period 2008 - 2019 the species was found in more than ten localities of six floristic regions. Populations usually number less than 250 individuals. For some of the populations, data from recurrent observations are provided. We discuss the habitats and their management. The negative changes of the habitat quality during the last years for some of the localities are described as well. The species was evaluated as CR B1ab (iii) + 2ab (iii) according to the Red List of Bulgarian vascular plants. We reevaluate the status based on the improved knowledge. The species is still Critically Endangered in Bulgaria, but B2ab (iii, v) status better corresponds with recent data. Five of the known localities fall within the boundaries of Natura 2000 SCIs.

Keywords

Bulgarian flora, *Dactylorhiza kalopissii*, distribution, conservation

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